

INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES OF MXENE/GRAPHENE/POLYMER MATRIX NANOCOMPOSITES

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Introduction

- The outstanding effect of nano reinforcement on mechanical properties of nanocomposites is related with high specific surface area of nanofiller, strong filler-matrix interfacial adhesion as well as the properties of filler and polymer matrix. In recent years, two-dimensional (2D) nanomaterials have received significant attention from academia and industries, with graphene (GP) as the most popular material due to its excellent electric, mechanical, and other properties. The properties of GP and polymer matrix interfaces are known. GP has hydrophobic surface resulting in agglomeration, poor compatibility, weak interfaces and insufficient mechanical reinforcement effect. To improve the surface properties of GP modification of surface properties is necessary.
- Recently, a new family of 2D nanomaterials MXene was discovered. MXene has uncommon combination of metallic conductivity and hydrophilicity that is the key to the promise these materials have engendered. Hydrophilicity is an important feature of MXenes that could determine the strong interface interaction between MXene nanosheet and matrix and dispersibility in polymers. In order to utilize the advantages of MXene in MXene/GP/polymer matrix nanocomposites, a comprehensive understanding of MXene surface properties is crucial.
- The aim of this study is to determine the interfacial adhesion and compatibility at MXene -matrix interface and the overall composite performance.

Materials and Methods

- The FE analysis of mechanical behaviour of Mxene/GP/epoxy nanocomposites were performed by DIGIMAT™ and ANSYS.

Mechanical properties of MXene, graphene and epoxy

Material properties	2D nanoparticles		Matrix
	Ti ₃ C ₂ [1]	Graphene [2]	Epoxy [3]
Young modulus (GPa)	330	1000	2.74
Tensile strength	17 GPa	110 GPa	80.3 MPa
Elongation at break (%)	9.5	17	5.3
Poisson's ratio	0.23	0.17	0.4

FE Model Generation

Representative volume elements of MXene/GP/epoxy matrix nanocomposites

Conclusions

- MXene exhibits a high surface energy (52.1 – 72.5 mJ/m²) and is able to form strong adhesive bonds with polymer matrix.
- Addition of 2.5 vol.% of MXenes in the GP/epoxy composition increases modulus, but slightly decreases strength of nanocomposite independently on the interaction at GP and epoxy matrix interface.
- The higher volume fraction of MXenes (10 vol. %) significantly increases Young modulus and strength of the MXene/GP/epoxy matrix nanocomposite.

References

- [1] A. Lipatov, H. Lu, M. Alhabeb, B. Anasori, A. Gruverman, Y. Gogotsi, A. Sinitskii "Elastic properties of 2D Ti₃C₂T_x MXene monolayers and bilayers". Science Advances, Vol. 4, pp 1-7, 2018.
- [2] P. Solankya, V. Sharmab, K. Ghatak, J. Kashyap, D. Dattab "The inherent behavior of graphene flakes in water: A molecular dynamics study". Computational Materials Science, Vol. 162, pp 140-147, 2019.
- [3] Y.-K. Yang, L.-J. Yu, R.-G. Peng, Y.-L. Huang, Ch.-E. He, H.-Y. Liu, X.-B. Wang, X.-L. Xie and Y.-W. Mai "Incorporation of liquid-like multiwalled carbon nanotubes into an epoxy matrix by solvent-free processing". Nanotechnology, Vol. 23, pp 1-10, 2012.

Results and Discussion

Study of MXene and epoxy interfacial strength by contact angle measurements

- Surface tension γ_s for MXene, epoxy resin and MXene/epoxy composites was calculated from the contact angles measurements applying Harmonic mean approach.
- MXene exhibits a high surface energy ($\gamma = 52.1 - 72.5$ mJ/m²). Surface energy of epoxy resin is 46 – 59 mJ/m² that is lower than results for MXene.
- The work of adhesion of epoxy and MXene was found to be $W = 130.5$ mJ/m².

Mechanical behaviour of MXene/GP/epoxy nanocomposite

Influence of the GP and epoxy interface strength on the $\sigma - \epsilon$ relationship of nanocomposite

Influence of GP and MXene on the $\sigma - \epsilon$ relationship of epoxy nanocomposite

Stress-strain curves for MXene/GP/epoxy nanocomposites at different strength at GP and epoxy interface

Stress-strain curves for MXene/GP/epoxy nanocomposites at different MXene content

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